

Women Participation in Community and Social Development Project (CSDP) in Ondo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined women participation in Community and Social Development Project (CSDP) in Ondo State, Nigeria. The data obtained from 120 women were analyzed using frequency counts, percentage, mean as well as Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Chi square. The mean age of the respondents was 42 years. More than half (56.7%) of the respondents had average family size of 6 persons. Most (73.0%) of the respondents were ordinary members of Community Groups and 35 percent were relatively low income earners with the average income of ₦ 18,700. About 86 percent of the respondents indicated farming as their livelihood activities. The level of participation was low with a grand mean score of 2.03 and this could be due to some perceived factors affecting participation in CSDP. Significant relationships existed between age, family size and level of women participation in CSDP. The Chi-square result showed that significant association existed between social status, occupation and level of women participation in CSDP. More sensitization on CSDP projects is therefore recommended and women should be encouraged to take up leadership position. Development strategies and plan should also be well structured to enhance the mobilization of youths and middle aged women in the Project.

KEYWORDS: Women, Participation, CSDP

1. INTRODUCTION

Community needs development for solving their problems, thus increasing their capacity will enable them to participate fully in the economy of the nation. In Nigeria, several development efforts have been made by the Federal Government to bring about development in the rural areas. This is because development enhances the livelihood of people including women which increases agricultural production in the rural areas and brings about food security in the family and nation as a whole. It should be noted that every community in Nigeria needs development, especially, in terms of social amenities (Adegboye, 2005). Community development is a conscious and deliberate effort aimed at helping communities to recognize their needs and to assure in carrying out responsibilities for solving their problems, thereby increasing their capacity to participate fully in the lives of the nation (Ekong, 2003).

Community-Driven Development (CDD) programs offer a potentially attractive way to drive the selection of development projects down to the local level, allowing the communities to determine projects and to select beneficiaries themselves (Mansuri and Rao, 2004). Community-Driven Development is fast-growing mechanism that builds on the empowerment of the affected population by giving them control over planning decision

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and investment resources (Mansuri and Rao, 2004). Community and Social Development Project (CSDP) is a World Bank assisted development project which utilizes Community-Driven Development (CDD) approach to carry out its activities in eight sectors namely, water, health, education, transport, electricity, environment and natural resource, socio-economic (market, civic center / skill acquisition center, hall and television viewing center) and gender and vulnerable group (Ondo State Community and Social Development Agency, ODCSDA, 2009).

Social inclusiveness is one of the key features of CDD programs under CSDP, for the purpose of fostering involvement of the poor and marginalized people such as women in such interventions. Women's domestic roles are caretakers of the family's health and managers of households (Ahmed, 2008). Nevertheless, the ability of women to contribute to the development process depends on the extent to which they participate in the decision-making process at all levels. Participation which is the active involvement of the beneficiaries in the CSDP project empowers the vulnerable and women. When beneficiaries also make decisions, participation becomes a self-initiated action, which is known as the exercise of voice and choice or empowerment (Mansuri and Rao, 2004). The cornerstone of

Community-Driven Development (CDD) initiatives used in CSDP is the active involvement of members of a defined community in at least some aspects of project design and implementation (Mansuri and Rao, 2004). Okunlola (2011) reveals that CDD seeks to use the instrumentality of participation to empower the excluded group and hence give them both voice and relevance. One of the objectives of Community and Social Development Project (CSDP) is to empower the marginalized people such as women in order to improve on the standard of living of these women.

A number of projects have been executed in Ondo State using Community-Driven Development (CDD) approach under Community and Social Development Project (CSDP). Community Social Development Project (CSDP) which was assisted by World Bank was established in Ondo State on 17th September, 2009 in Ondo State with the overall goal to improve access of the poor and the vulnerable such as women to services for Human Development (ODCSDA, 2012). In order to enhance programme sustainability, participation by marginalized people such as women in the institutions that make decisions that affect their lives must be encouraged (Binswanger, 2003). Hence, participation of women is very crucial to the success of any development project in Nigeria (Kawani and Pernia, 2002). Ekong (2003) asserted that infrastructural development is sine-qua-non to improving the living standard of majority of the nation's populace. Therefore, participation of these rural women in CSDP projects such as potable water supply facilities, construction of roads/bridges, health facilities, market facilities, acquisition of skills centers, hall and viewing centers etc., which were assisted by World Bank will affect their performances and productions in their various livelihood activities.

The extent at which women have participated in the project must be known due to their important roles in the family and contribution to the national economy. Hence, it is imperative to carry out research on the participation of women in Community and Social Development Project (CSDP) in Ondo State to ascertain the level of participation of women in CSDP projects for improved livelihood activities. Therefore, the broad objective of this study was to determine the participation of women in Community and Social Development Project (CSDP) in Ondo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study addressed the following; describe the socio-economic characteristics of women that are involved in Community and Social Development Project; determine the extent of the respondents' awareness of Community and Social Development Project; examine the level of participation of women at various levels of the Community and Social Development Project; and determine the perceived factors affecting women participation in Community and Social Development Project in the study area. The research hypothesis for this study was;

H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between socioeconomic characteristics of women and their level of participation in the Community and Social Development Project.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study area

The study area was Ondo State. It comprises of 3 senatorial districts of North, Central and South and Akure is the State capital. Ondo State is made up of 18 Local Government Areas (LGAs). Ondo State is bounded on the East by Ogun and Osun

States on the West by Edo and Delta, on North by Ekiti and Kogi States and to the South by Atlantic Ocean. Ondo State is an agrarian State and various Community-Driven Development (CDD) projects have been established in the State. The population of the study includes women that are beneficiaries of CSDP in Ondo State.

2.2. Data collection and sampling procedure

The primary data were obtained through the use of pre-tested structured interview schedule. The instrument used was designed to gather relevant information on the socio-economic characteristics of women that are involved in Community and Social Development Project; identify livelihood activities of the respondents; examine the level of participation of women at various levels of the Community and Social Development Project; and determine the perceived factors affecting women participation in Community and Social Development Project in the study area.

Multi-stage sampling procedure was used for this study. Sixteen benefitting Local Government Areas in Ondo state were purposively selected due to their participation in CSDP, out of which three Local Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly selected. These are Ile-Oluji, Odigbo, and Owo Local Government Areas. From each of the selected Local Government Areas, four communities that have benefitted from Community and Social Development Project were purposively selected. Each community was divided into four geographical wards, from which two wards were purposively selected based on involvement in the CSDP projects. From each ward, five respondents were interviewed, making a total of ten respondents per community and a total sample size of one hundred and twenty respondents.

2.3. Analytical technique

Descriptive statistic such as frequency counts, percentages and mean were used to describe the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents. The extent to which the respondents were aware of CSDP projects were measured using 4-point Likert scale as MA =Much Aware (4), A = Aware (3), JA =Just Aware (2), NA =Not Aware (1). Key for decision scale: MA = (≥ 3.50), A = (2.5 - 3.49), JA = (1.5 - 2.49), NA = (< 1.5).

Respondents' level of participation was measured using a 4-point Likert scale as High (4), Moderate (3), Low (2), No participation (1) in the listed projects. Key for decision scale: High = (≥ 3.5), Moderate = (2.5 - 3.49), Low = (1.5 - 2.39), No Participation = (< 1.5). Also, the perceived factors affecting participation of the respondents were indicated using 5-point Likert scale of Strongly agreed (5), Agreed (4), Undecided (3), Strongly disagreed (2), Disagreed (1) on factors listed affecting participation in CSDP projects. Key for decision: Strongly Agreed = (≥ 4.5), Agreed = (3.5 - 4.49), Undecided = (2.5 - 3.49), Disagreed = (1.5 - 2.49), Strongly Disagreed = (< 1.5). A total of twelve items were included in this scale with rankings. Chi-square and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used to test the hypothesis.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents

The result from Table 1 revealed the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents in the study area. The mean age of the respondents in this study was 42 years. The

result further revealed that 31.7 percent of the respondents had the age range of 41-50 years (middle aged class), implying influence on their active participation in the Community and Social Development Project projects that are in line with their production in order to improve their living standard. This finding further agrees with the study of Mafimisebi (2007) that respondents within this age limit (41-50 years) are in the economically active age bracket to undertake various livelihood activities. Also, it was reported that most (70.8%) of the respondents were married. This would influence their decision positively to participate in CSDP. This finding agrees with Farinde *et al.* (2004) that seventy percent of women who participated in the rural community project were married. It was also revealed that the mean household size of the respondents was 6 persons. The result revealed that most (56.7%) of the respondents had 1-5 persons. This means labour contribution in participation during CSDP activities could be affected and average family members would benefit from these projects undertaken in the community. This finding agrees with Ekong (2003) that household size has positive influence on the level of participation in the programme.

Furthermore, the study showed that 38.3 percent had primary education. This means that most of the respondents had low formal level of education. Also, 15 percent of the respondents had no formal education. This implies that the level of education might affect the respondents' exposure to sources of information and participation Community Social Development Project that are related to their livelihood activities. The result further showed that most (73.3%) of the

respondents were ordinary members of the community who did not belong to any committee in the group. The implication of this is that the ordinary members of the community groups are followers and not leaders who are legitimizers to affirm or support the commencement of the projects. This assertion is in agreement with Lawko (2006) who stated that individually, women have a low social position.

In addition, the findings revealed that 46.7 percent of the respondents were practicing farming. This distribution shows the relative importance of farming to other occupations in the study area, implying that the most of the respondents (farmers) would like to participate in any project that may improve their livelihood activities. This finding supports Ogunbameru *et al.* (2006) that majority of women were involved in agricultural activities. The result further revealed that among the respondents that were practicing farming, most (80.4%) of the respondents were into crop production. This implies that respondents would like to participate in the CSDP projects that are relevant to crop production in order to bring improvement on their livelihoods. Moreover, it was revealed that the mean monthly income was ₦18,000.00. About 38.3 percent of the respondents earned between ₦10,001 - ₦20,000 as monthly income. This implies that the respondents' relative low income could affect the level of participation in raising the contribution of counterpart fund in Community and Social Development Project. This finding agrees with Sallau and Rahman (2007) who reported an annual income of less than ₦100,000 among rural women.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents' Socioeconomic Characteristics

Variables	Frequency	Percentages	Mean
Age (years)			
≥30	20	16.7	42
31- 40	29	24.2	
41-50	38	31.7	
51- 60	22	18.3	
61 and above	11	9.2	
Marital Status			
Single	25	20.8	
Married	85	70.8	
Divorced	04	3.3	
Household size			
1-5	68	56.7	6
6- 10	32	26.7	
11- 15	15	12.5	
16- 20	5	4.1	
Educational level			
Non formal education	18	15.0	
Primary education	46	38.3	
Secondary education	18	15.0	
Tertiary education	38	31.7	
Social status			
Member	88	73.3	
Committed member	28	23.3	
Leader	04	3.3	
Occupation			
Farming	56	46.7	
Public service	26	21.7	
Trading	21	17.5	
Artisan	11	9.2	
Private service	06	5.0	

Types of farming			
Crop production	45	80.4	
Animal production	01	1.8	
Crop and animal production	10	17.8	
Monthly income			
≤ ₦10,000	41	34.2	₦18,000
₦10,001- ₦20,000	46	38.3	
₦20,001- ₦30,000	14	11.7	
₦30,001- ₦40,000	09	7.5	
₦40,001- ₦50,000	04	3.3	
≥ ₦50,001 and above	06	5.0	

Source: Field survey, 2013.

3.2. Awareness of Community and Social Development Projects in Ondo State

Table 2 revealed that the respondents were aware of provision of potable water project with a mean score of 2.88 and were aware of the construction of roads and bridges project with a mean score of 2.53. This means that the respondents were aware of the provision of potable water and construction of roads and bridges only in Community and Social Development Project.

The result also revealed that the mean was less than 2.5 for other projects such as the construction of health/maternity project ($\bar{X}=2.23$), the construction of community hall and viewing centre ($\bar{X}=1.93$), construction of skill acquisition ($\bar{X}=1.76$) and the construction of market project ($\bar{X}=2.11$). It was revealed that awareness of Community and Social Development Projects in Ondo State by the respondents had a grand mean of 2.24. This means that the respondents were just aware of these micro-projects. The implication is that the respondents would need more sensitization on the micro-projects by CSDP that might improve their livelihood activities in order to participate and have positive perception of the effects in the CSDP projects on their livelihood activities. This finding agrees with Lakwo (2006) that low awareness of community development projects by women affects their participation in such projects to be able to improve their livelihoods.

Table2: Awareness of Community and Social Development Projects in Ondo State

Project Type	Mean	Decision
Provision of Potable water	2.88	Aware
Construction of Roads and Bridges	2.53	Aware
Construction of Health/ Maternity Centre	2.23	Just Aware
Construction of Community Hall and Viewing Centre	1.93	Just Aware
Construction of Skill Acquisition	1.76	Just Aware
Construction of Market	2.11	Just Aware

Grand mean= 2.24

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

3.3. Level of Participation of Respondents in Community and Social Development Projects

The result from Table 3 revealed the level of participation of the respondents at various levels of Community and Social Development Projects. The Table revealed that most of the respondents (15.6%) participated in identification of needs with the highest mean score of 2.38 while 13.1 percent participated in prioritization of needs ($\bar{X} = 2.17$).

Furthermore, the result showed that few (7.8%) of the respondents participated in contribution of counterpart fund ($\bar{X} = 1.83$) and 8.5 percent participated in the project implementation ($\bar{X} = 1.81$). This implies that women participation in the contribution to counterpart fund and ability to participate in project implementation could be affected by their low level of income and their social status in the community as ordinary members rather as leaders. This observation agrees with the findings of Lakwo (2006) who found that women’s non-participation recorded an exceptionally high in community project implementation.

It was revealed that activities involved in CSDP projects had a grand mean of 2.03. This implies a low participation of the respondents in CSDP projects.

Table3: Participation of Respondents in Community and Social Development

Activities Involved	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Mobilization of community members for project	67	12.2	2.24
Identification of needs	86	15.6	2.38
Prioritization of needs	72	13.1	2.17
Election of community project implementation members	55	10.0	1.81
Contribution of counterpart fund	43	7.8	1.83
Participating in the project implementation	47	8.5	1.81
Awareness creation on project	55	10.0	1.98
Labour contribution during project implementation	68	12.4	2.10
Monitoring of project	57	10.4	1.97

Project*Multiple responses Grand Mean = 2.03

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

3.4. Perceived Factors Affecting Women Participation in Community and Social Development Project (CSDP)

The result from Table 4 revealed that 90.9 percent of the respondents agreed that lack of adequate information affects the level of participation in CSDP ($\bar{X} = 4.32$). This implies that provision of adequate information would enhance participation in CSDP. The finding agrees with Kongolo and Bamgose (2002) that lack of adequate information was one of the most important factors contributing to the inactive participation of rural women in developments. About 80.3 percent find it difficult to pay counterpart fund for CSDP project ($\bar{X} = 4.13$). This implies that inability to pay counterpart should be considered in order to enhance respondents' participation in CSDP. Also, 73.3 percent political biased-mindedness affects CSDP projects ($\bar{X} = 4.08$). The implication is that allocation of resources to beneficiaries should be monitored to enhance participation.

On the other hand, the result revealed that 58.4 percent of the respondents agreed that level of income influences participation in CSDP projects ($\bar{X} = 3.58$). This implies that respondents with low income would find it difficult to participate in money contribution during project activities and users' fee. This finding agrees with Qamar (2005) who observed that payment of user fees by poor farmers who produce low-value crops is a major problem in low-income countries. On the statement that participation in CSDP projects depends on age bracket, the respondents were undecided ($\bar{X} = 3.28$). This implies age was a probability among factors affecting women participation in CSDP projects.

Table4: Perceived Factors Affecting Women Participation in CSDP

Statements	Mean	Decision	Rank
Lack of adequate information affects participation in CSDP projects	4.32	Agreed	1
Inability to pay counterpart fund limits CSDP project implementation	4.13	Agreed	2
Political biased-mindedness affects CSDP projects	4.08	Agreed	3
Lack of trust and confidence affects CSDP projects	4.01	Agreed	4
Influence of discrimination/ Gender biased affects CSDP projects	3.75	Agreed	5
Relevance of projects to women creates apathy towards CSDP projects	3.72	Agreed	6
Level of education affects participation in CSDP projects	3.63	Agreed	7
Cultural values and belief affects CSDP projects	3.61	Agreed	8
Lack of operational knowledge/language affects CSDP projects	3.58	Agreed	9
Level of income influences participation in CSDP projects	3.58	Agreed	10
Participation in CSDP projects depends on age bracket	3.28	Undecided	11
Religious affects participation in CSDP projects	2.63	Disagreed	12

Grand mean: 3.7

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

3.5. HO₁: There is no significant relationship between the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents and their participation in the Community and Social Development Project.

The result of the chi-square was used to ascertain the probability relationship of respondents' socioeconomic characteristics and their participation in Community Social Development Project (CSDP). Table 5 showed that social status in the community ($\chi^2=32.8^*$, $p<0.05$) and occupations of the respondents ($\chi^2=38.8^*$, $p<0.05$) were the socioeconomic factors that influenced respondents' participation in the micro-projects. There is a positive significant relationship between social status and women participation and this suggests the leaders in the community, especially legitimizers are interested in the micro-projects because of their involvement. This could be due to the fact that those who have been exposed to development activities outside their community are most willing to have such experience in their community because of the benefits such respondents are going to derive from such projects to enhance their production. Also, a positive significant relationship between occupation and women participation suggests the relevance of the occupation with the projects would enhance participation.

There was no significant association between socioeconomic factors like type of marriage, level of education, religion, and participation in the CSDP project. The implication of this is that these socio-economic characteristics did not have any influence on the women participation in the Community Social Development Project. This implies that marriage, level of education and religious were not factors affecting participation.

In addition to the above result from Table 5, the findings from Table 6 also indicates that age and family size were the socioeconomic factors that influenced participation in the micro-projects by the respondents. There is a significant relationship between age ($r=0.326$, $p<0.05$), the family size ($r=0.258$, $p<0.05$) and participation in CSDP which indicates that the age of the respondents and family size affect their participation in CSDP projects. This could be because the older people are eager to enjoy some social facilities and also have more time for community work. The issue of family size affecting the respondents' participation could be because more labour would be available for project activities. Imoh (2004) found a significant relationship between family size and participation of women in community development. The hypothesis is therefore rejected for this variable. There was no significant relationship between income ($r=0.047$, $p<0.05$), as a socio-economic characteristic and participation.

Table5: Chi-Square Result of Socioeconomic Characteristics and Participation in Community and Social Development Project (CSDP)

Variables	χ^2	Df	p- value	Decision
Marital status	11.2	5	0.192	NS
Level of education	12.9	8	0.382	NS
Religion	6.3	3	0.181	NS
Social status	32.8*	3	0.000	S
Oscupation	38.8*	5	0.000	S

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

Table6: Correlations between Socioeconomic Characteristics and Participation of Community and Social Development Project (CSDP)

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Age	0.326*	0.00	S
Family size	0.258*	0.00	S
Monthly income	0.047	0.620	NS

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

4. Conclusion and Policy Issues

The study was carried out to determine women participation in Community and Social Development Project (CSDP) in Ondo State, Nigeria. Our findings revealed that most of the ordinary members of the social group fell within the age of 41-50 years and were fundamentally farmers. Majority of the respondents were aware of construction of potable water facilities, roads and bridges in the area. It was observed, however, that the level of women participation in the project was low. This could not be unconnected with various factors such as lack of adequate information, influence of gender discrimination, age bracket, level of income and inability to pay counterpart fund.

We proffer that strategies that will enhance the mobilization of youths and middle aged women in the programme should be put in place. Women should be encouraged to take up leadership position due to their social status as ordinary members so that they will be able to influence decisions towards participation in the Community and Social Development Project. This could be by creating more portfolios for women in the Community Project Management Committee. More sensitization about Community and Social Development Project should be created using various media aids, government agencies, Community Based Organizations, Non-Governmental Organizations and religions Institutions. Finally, development strategies and plan should be well structured to improve farm productivity due to its significance as the major occupation of these women in order to improve their level of income.

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